

Locus	Dye	Singleplex temperature (°C)	Multiplex temperature (°C)	Size range (bp)	Repeated motif	Primer sequences (5'-3')
M74	FAM	60	59	223-268	AAT(Trinucleotides)	(F) GGAGTTGATTGTCATTCTTATTTACCC (R) AGCCTAAGCAGGCAGGTTT
M109	FAM	58	59	166-214	ACAG(Tetranucleotides)	(F) TCCACGTACGGTGTTTAATTG (R) ACAGACCAGAGACCACTGATG
M145	FAM	55	56	150-171	ATT(Trinucleotides)	(F) GTCCTTGATGTGAGGCCAG (R) TCGCCAAATTAAGCACGAG
M164	FAM	59	56	195-228	AAT(Trinucleotides)	(F) GAAGCGGGCACATCACTTG (R) GTCCCGGAAAGTCCCAAAC
M170	FAM	59	59	132-171	ATT(Trinucleotides)	(F) TGGAACCTTTGGCAACTCCG (R) CCTAGAGTGCAAATGTACGCC
M182	PET	59	59	195-243	AAT(Trinucleotides)	(F) AGTGTACATCTCCAGAAATGGG (R) TGCCTCCAATGTTCAAGGTTTC
M186	PET	58	56	168-213	AAT(Trinucleotides)	(F) TGTGCGTTTGTACCATTG (R) ACTCCATAATCTGTATCCTGTTTCG

Supplemental table 1) Characterisation of the newly developed microsatellites loci of *Psalmatophanes barretoii*. (F= forward and R = reverse) (**Bold** distinguishes the different multiplex temperature)

Morphological trait	Burned vs Unburned	Altitude	Altitude * Area (Burned vs UnBurned)
Pronotum length	<i>F = 5.45</i> <i>p = 0.02</i>	F = 3.24 p = 0.07	F = 0.64 p = 0.43
Pronotum width	<i>F = 4.7</i> <i>p = 0.03</i>	F = 1.71 p = 0.19	F = 0.46 p = 0.5
Femur length	F = 2.89 p = 0.09	<i>F = 8.23</i> <i>p < 0.005</i>	F = 0.21 p = 0.64
Body length	<i>F = 5.61</i> <i>p = 0.02</i>	F = 1.4 p = 0.24	F = 0.5 p = 0.48
Body weight	F = 2.42 p = 0.12	F = 0.31 p = 0.58	F = 0.004 p = 0.95
Wing width	<i>F = 11.37</i> <i>p < 0.005</i>	<i>F = 6.76</i> <i>p = 0.01</i>	F = 2.76 p = 0.1

Supplemental Table 2) The relationship between morphological traits and different environmental conditions tested by ANOVA . (The significance indicates with *italic* and **bold**)